

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The role of brand image, electronic word of mouth and customer satisfaction in building repurchase intention in e-marketplace

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Abstract

E-marketplaces are not only used as sites for carrying out online buying and selling transactions, but also offer features that are superior to other e-marketplaces. Buying and selling activities through e-marketplaces have grown rapidly compared to when e-marketplaces were first established. Today's e-marketplaces not only act as buying and selling sites, but also have interesting features. The intensive use of live streaming and live shopping features attracts the attention of potential consumers to find out more about the product. This phenomenon can be used as an opportunity to offer products and attract new consumers, or even attract old consumers to make repeat purchases. e-marketplaces has business opportunities by increasing interest in repeat purchases even though competition between e-marketplaces is increasingly crowded. This article discusses the influence of brand image and electronic word of mouth on repurchase intention through customer satisfaction in e-market place.

Keywords: Brand Image; Electronic Word of Mouth; Customer Satisfaction; Repurchase Intention; E-Market Place

1. Introduction

With increasingly widespread and sophisticated technological developments, the role of the internet in everyday life cannot be underestimated. Based on the results of a report by We Are Social, as many as 212.9 million people in Indonesia at the beginning of 2023 were internet users compared to the previous year and as many as 178.94 million internet users were also e-marketplace users (Mustajab, 2023). In 2019, Indonesia was ranked 1st out of 10 countries in the world as the country with the largest e-marketplace growth, namely 78% (Ministry of Communication and Information, 2019), of course this proves that the impact of technology is increasingly being felt by society and business people, especially in online shopping activities. Apart from that, with the increase in the e-marketplace trend, business actors can use this opportunity to develop their business and access a wider market share.

E-marketplaces are not only used as sites for carrying out online buying and selling transactions, but also offer features that are superior to other e-marketplaces. Buying and selling activities through e-marketplaces have grown rapidly compared to when e-marketplaces were first established. Today's e-marketplaces not only act as buying and selling sites, but also have interesting features. Some related features are that through e-marketplace consumers can make bill payments, chat between e-marketplace users, play games, live shopping, and various payment options such as via digital wallets or paylater systems.

The intensive use of live streaming and live shopping features attracts the attention of potential consumers to find out more about the product. This phenomenon can be used as an opportunity to offer products and attract new consumers, or even attract old consumers to make repeat purchases. Repurchase intention is a real action by consumers in consuming similar services or products from the same seller repeatedly (Tong & Subagio, 2020). According to Jaya &

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Putri (2021) repurchase intention is a consumer's decision to buy goods or services again from the same business after making a previous purchase, and usually creates a tendency for consumers to make continuous purchases.

Repurchase intentions for a product or service offered can be influenced by brand image. Tjiptono (2011, in Yunaida, 2017) states that brand image is an explanation of consumer associations and beliefs regarding a particular brand. Brand image is something that can be seen and assessed even before consumers use a product or service. This statement is supported by Yunaida (2017) if the brand image of a product is bad, the potential purchase percentage made by consumers will be smaller. Repurchases made by consumers are based on memories or consequences received by consumers from a product.

Repurchase intentions can also be influenced by electronic word of mouth, where in live streaming or live shopping sessions, sellers can provide reviews or impressions that come from both themselves and others in using and receiving the results of the product. Live streaming sessions that can be carried out on the Tokopedia platform for a maximum of two hours and focus on important points about the product can arouse the curiosity of other users, resulting in the product going viral or being widely sought after, which can improve brand image.

The popularity of the live streaming feature as a medium for selling products has a positive effect on business people, direct interaction is able to encourage consumers to make purchases by convincing consumers of the quality of the product or the price provided (Dwiastono, 2022). Based on a survey conducted by Kadence International, the results of research conducted by Sari & Rastini (2022) prove that e-WOM has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intentions. The research results of Putri & Sumaryono (2021) prove that electronic word of mouth has a positive influence on repurchase intentions through e-marketplaces. Electronic word of mouth is often used as an information medium by consumers before making purchasing decisions. The higher the e-WOM carried out by a company, the higher the buying interest.

Some consumer considerations in making repeat purchases can be caused by several factors, such as the satisfaction that consumers have after using the product. Customer satisfaction is one of the determining factors that can influence customers in determining repurchase intentions (Tan & Brahmana, 2019). The results of research by Pratama & Yulianthini (2022) and Chania, et al. (2022) proves that customer satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on repurchase decisions, research results (Baehaqi, et al., 2022) prove that customer satisfaction has a significant influence on consumer purchasing decisions.

Based on this background, e-marketplaces has business opportunities by increasing interest in repeat purchases even though competition between e-marketplaces is increasingly crowded. Looking at previous research, research conducted by Gumilang, et al., (2021) proves that brand image and electronic word of mouth have a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention and customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention and is able to mediate the influence of brand image and electronic word of mouth on repurchase intention. This article discusses the influence of brand image and electronic word of mouth on repurchase intention through customer satisfaction.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Brand Image

A company or business needs to create and build a good brand image so that more consumers remember the brand, because the brand is always attached to the existing business. According to Shihab & Siregar (2023), because brand image creates trust in consumers, brand image has the ability to influence consumers' thoughts when making purchases. According to Girsang, et al. (2020) brand image is a consumer's perception of the uniqueness of a company or product so that it can be recognized and differentiated from competitors, thereby growing consumer trust in the brand. Consumer perceptions about a product with related indirect elements will create a brand image when combined (Suwarsih, et al., 2021). Various brand-related elements such as names, symbols, terms, designs, and other elements. Brand image is an overall view that forms information and experiences that can be seen and assessed by consumers before using the product (Nisa & Sari, 2023).

Consumer perceptions regarding the entire brand are formed through information and experiences received by consumers in the past (Putri & Yasa, 2022). According to (Indarto, et al., 2022) the basis of brand image consists of a number of factors, such as brand experience and product category, product quality, price, promotion, customer expectations, and usage situations. Therefore, brand image determines and influences purchasing decisions made by consumers, so that the higher the brand image a business has, the greater the consumer's tendency to make purchases.

Likewise, when the brand image of a business tends to be low, consumers will make fewer purchasing decisions due to the possibility of consumers switching to other products provided by brands from different businesses. A strong brand image has a good impact and benefits for the brand, such as popularity, the brand can retain consumers and attract the attention of potential consumers in a wider range.

According to Kotler & Keller (2016) the elements that form a brand image are brand strength, brand favorability and brand uniqueness. Brand strength is the ability that consumers have to think about information from a brand, such as the logo and brand name, and how consumers process and manage all the information that consumers receive by sensory neurons in the brain as part of the brand image. Brand favorability consists of the large variety of choices available to meet consumer needs and desires, product affordability, convenience of getting the goods needed, and goods that come from well-known companies. Being able to give a distinctive impression and a significant difference from other companies is what makes a brand unique, so this is the basic reason for consumers to choose that brand. Researchers emphasize the elements that form brand image to see how the factors that form brand image create consumers' perceptions and impressions of the brand. According to Kotler & Keller (2009, in Darmawan & Pramudana, 2022) there are 3 components that form a brand image, namely:

2.2. Brand Strength

The public can recognize the company's brand, because it already has advantages over competing brands. The brand's advantages are physical, such as the function of all existing facilities and the appearance of the facilities. Apart from that, brand excellence can also be used as a connecting medium between companies and consumers. The relationship between the two must continue to be maintained so that the brand can continue to survive in competition. logos

2.2.1. Brand Favorability

The ability of a brand to be liked by consumers. A brand that has appeal so that it is preferred by consumers. This attraction can be used by companies to make their products superior to competitors. Meet consumer wants and needs, many choices, features,

2.2.2. Brand Uniqueness

Brands have unique qualities that can be seen by the public to differentiate them from competing brands. That way, the brand will be increasingly remembered and recognized by consumers and potential consumers. Brands have the opportunity to develop and innovate over a long period of time, the opportunity to attract new investors for larger companies, and consumers are increasingly loyal to the brand.

2.2.3. Electronic Word of Mouth

The increasing development of technology and the use of social media can influence purchasing decisions made by consumers, especially based on opinions and reviews on social media. Due to the wider reach of the internet network and the faster distribution rate, more opportunities and problems are being encountered (Gumilang, et al., 2021). According to Farzin & Fattahi (2018) eWOM is a transfer of information originating from social media or online forums which can influence consumer purchasing decisions. According to Qirana, et al. (2021) eWOM is an improvement on WOM via the internet network. WOM itself is a traditional process of transferring and disseminating information, consumers can recommend products to people around them. It can also be done through social media or other internet sites, known as eWOM and can come from unknown people (Hariono, 2018).

Electronic word of mouth is a means of marketing communication, both directly and indirectly, originating from someone to provide an opinion about a product that has been used. eWOM is useful and used by consumers to find information about products before deciding to purchase. And if consumers receive benefits and feel satisfied with a product, eWOM can be an effective promotional media for introducing or recommending the product to others. Knowing the effectiveness of electronic word of mouth via the internet can help businesses convey messages and concentrate on the target audience (Poturak & Turkyilmaz, 2018). According to Nuseir (2019), when compared to claims and details about products provided by business people themselves, people prefer anonymous reviews or comments about products posted online. Dimensions that can be used to measure electronic word of mouth are intensity, valence of opinion, and content (Jalilvand, 2012; in Putri & Sienarta, 2023)

*Intensity:*The intensity of the number of opinions or reviews written by consumers regarding products on the internet via social media. The intensity of electronic word of mouth can be seen through the frequency of how many times consumers access internet network information to obtain information and how many times consumers participate in providing opinions or reviews and even statements.

Valence of Opinion: Comments or responses given by consumers regarding products, services or brands. Opinions given may relate to the quality, price, type or services provided via the internet network. Positive opinions from consumers arise from consumer expectations being met, resulting in consumer satisfaction. Negative opinions are given by consumers who feel dissatisfied or receive a bad experience.

Content (Konten){ Information about products contained in comments or responses written by consumers via the internet. The information received by consumers is based on the credibility and quality of the information conveyed by the information source.

2.2.4. Customer Satisfaction

Satisfaction or satisfaction results can vary depending on what is felt and received by consumers. Satisfaction comes from the Latin words *satis* and *facere*. *Satis* means good enough and *facere* means make. When combined, satisfaction means the product or service offered to consumers is able to provide satisfaction to consumers to a sufficient level. Or able to exceed consumer expectations when using the product. According to Worodiyanti & Maspiyah (2016), customer satisfaction is a reaction that arises from consumers in the form of feelings of happiness or disappointment regarding the fulfillment of expectations that can be achieved by a product after being used by consumers. Customer Satisfaction can be used as a benchmark by which companies or businesses can find out whether the products and services they offer meet consumer expectations (Putri & Yasa, 2022).

The reactions that arise from the experiences received by customers can be seen as an assessment of how consumers feel about a product when compared with expectations before purchasing the product and how consumers feel after using the product (Muthi & Utama, 2023). According to May, et al. (2017) define customer satisfaction as the emotional reaction felt by consumers after purchasing a product or service. According to Aini (2019), customer satisfaction can increase the income or profits received by a company or business because consumers are not too sensitive to price increases and are willing to pay more to get the products or services offered. Customer satisfaction can create better relationships between companies and consumers, consumer satisfaction can improve the company's reputation which creates trust in consumers and potential consumers, and the intensity of contributions given by consumers to the company can increase. According to Huang, et al. (2014) to measure customer satisfaction the following measuring dimensions can be used:

Customer Feelings: The performance provided by the company through goods or services that appear when consumer expectations are met. Good product or service performance will be recognized by consumers, which will have an impact on consumer contributions in the future.

Expected Performance: The company's performance in services and facilities to meet consumer expectations. Before consumers decide to purchase a good or service, consumer expectations begin to form. Consumer expectations are influenced by several factors, namely those related to the needs and desires that consumers want to experience, past experiences that consumers remember, the experiences of other people who use the same product or service, and promotional activities carried out by the company through advertising or other marketing media. .

2.2.5. Repurchase Intention

Repurchase intention is the act of repurchasing carried out by consumers for the same product or service. If consumers have made purchases and used products or services, consumers have the potential to make repeat purchases (Tong & Subagio, 2020). Repurchase intention is a goal pursued by several companies in similar fields to gain an advantage in competition (Rahmawati, et al., 2018). According to Pham, et al. (2018) repurchase intention is the consumer's desire to be involved in company or business activities in the future because they have achieved satisfaction. The satisfaction felt by consumers will create value for a product so that consumers have the intention to repurchase. Repurchase intention is defined as the desire that consumers have to make repeat purchases in the future based on the experience received by consumers (Anggaeni, et al., 2015).

Repurchase intention can arise based on previous purchasing experiences (Anhar & Sunaryo, 2018). According to Putri & Yasa, 2022) repurchase intention is a consumer's post-purchase action which is based on the satisfaction they feel with the product they have previously purchased. Repurchase intention and product performance that is more than expected leads to satisfaction, due to the impact between the performance perceived by consumers and the expected performance (Amoako, et al., 2021). Repurchase interest is in line with the level of satisfaction received by consumers. The higher the consumer's repurchase interest, the higher the consumer's satisfaction with the product (Azhari & Nurhadi, 2022). Repurchase interest can also increase consumer loyalty to the product (Wahyu, et al., 2020). Another impact that can be influenced by repurchase intention is increasing the company's profitability and income, because

consumers decide to purchase the same product or service. Dimensions for measuring repurchase intention, according to Huang, et al. (2014) can be used as follows:

Revisit Intention: The interest that consumers have in repurchasing a product in the future. The interest in making repeat purchases can encourage consumers to pay higher prices to obtain or use goods or services.

Additional purchase intention: The interest that consumers have in helping to purchase a product that has been used by other consumers. Or the interest that consumers have in joining a group to purchase a product of their own accord. Interest in helping to purchase products can be influenced by oneself, namely desires or preferred tastes for certain products or services and also by the influence of other people who have experience after using the product.

3. Discussion

The results of research conducted by Santana & Keni (2020) prove that brand image has a positive effect on customer satisfaction, consumers who buy products from well-known companies will feel satisfied. Consumers also feel satisfied when the brand they use has more product advantages compared to competitors (Yulianto, et al., 2019). In research by Girsang, et al. (2020) brand image that has been attached to a brand for a long period of time has the ability to provide a consistent image of trust to consumers when using the product. If the intensity of a brand's brand image increases, it can influence the level of satisfaction felt by consumers when using the product.

The results of research by Kuo & Nakhata (2019) prove that electronic word of mouth has a bias effect on customer satisfaction. This means that consumers who are exposed to positive eWOM before purchasing will show higher satisfaction in their experience when using the product. Meanwhile, consumers who were exposed to negative eWOM before purchasing showed lower satisfaction in the experience when using the product. The level of satisfaction received by consumers can be based on whether consumers make high or low efforts when searching for information about the product before purchasing the product. In research by Farhat, et al. (2019) eWOM is able to create consumer satisfaction when the eWOM received is positive eWOM.

Ellitan, et al. (2023) prove that customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention, companies that are able to fulfill what consumers want will create satisfaction, this satisfaction is what supports consumers' decisions to make repeat purchases as a result of the experience received by consumers. So, the satisfaction obtained and felt by consumers will increase the customer's intensity in making repeat purchases. The results of research by Girsang, et al. (2020) customer satisfaction is a consumer response regarding whether the product is able to meet consumer expectations and is able to provide trust so that the frequency of repurchase intention can increase. And also the research results of Yulianto, et al. (2019) consumer experience while using a product does not stop at the satisfaction felt by the consumer but can also encourage repurchase intention.

Research conducted by Girsang, et al. (2020) brands that have advantages, strengths and uniqueness compared to competing brands are able to influence repurchase intention. In research by Almirah & Indayani (2022), brand image has an influence on repurchase intention, the presence of a brand is able to produce an assessment of consumer trust in the brand to decide whether to repurchase or not. The more a brand is rated positively by consumers, the more positive assessments of the brand will increase. Komang, et al. (2017) also proves that brand image has a positive effect on repurchase intention. The better the brand image a brand has, the greater the potential for consumers to make repeat purchases. A good brand image plays an important role in consumer purchasing decisions. The Influence of Electronic Word of Mouth on Repurchase Intention

The higher the frequency of eWOM carried out by other consumers, the more influence it will have on repurchase intention (Putri & Pradhanawati, 2021). The results of research by Hidajat & Damayanti (2022) show that all information about products that is spread widely by people known and unknown is able to encourage repurchase intention. eWOM that spreads through social media has a wide scope, the better or worse the eWOM has an impact on higher or lower repurchase intention. Farhat et al. (2019) found that when the positive influence of eWOM has been generated, it can create customer satisfaction which leads to consumer intention to purchase a product or brand. In research by Ginting, et al. (2023) and Saodin (2021) good eWOM can increase customer satisfaction and will influence an increase in consumers' repurchase intention.

4. Conclusion

Customer satisfaction is also influenced by the trust that consumers have in remembering the brand. Because consumers already have the confidence to remember the brand, this condition adds to the uniqueness of a company or product so that it can be recognized and differentiated from other companies or products. A good brand image is able to foster higher trust from consumers so that consumers get more satisfaction. Consumers pay more attention to the brand of the product they purchase so that if the brand has advantages as strength and uniqueness, consumers will feel more satisfied. The better the brand image of a company, the higher the level of consumer satisfaction when using the products offered. A brand image that has been attached to a brand for a long period of time has the ability to provide a consistent image of trust to consumers when using the product. The first thing consumers do is read comments or responses given by other consumers before purchasing a product through a digital marketing platform application. However, even if these conditions occur, there is still the possibility that consumers will not be satisfied with the products they purchase, which will affect the satisfaction felt by consumers. This can happen because there is a difference in the satisfaction felt by consumers themselves and the satisfaction of other consumers, based on the reviews given. In other words, different experiences between consumers themselves and other consumers create different satisfaction.

The feeling of pleasure felt by consumers when purchasing products through an e-market application is a reaction that arises from fulfilling expectations achieved after using the product. The happy reaction felt by consumers also increases consumer interest in helping other people make purchases on e-marketplaces. This is based on the potential for consumers to make repeat purchases after making a purchase or using an e-marketplace application. If the satisfaction felt by consumers is high enough, this will increase the consumer's decision to make repeat purchases as a result of the experience received by the consumer. Customer satisfaction is an illustration of whether the product is able to meet consumer expectations and is able to provide trust so that the frequency of repurchase intention can increase. The consumer's experience while using the product does not stop at the satisfaction felt by the consumer but can also encourage repurchase intention. Brand image has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention. Brands that have advantages, strengths and uniqueness compared to competing brands are able to influence repurchase intention. The presence of a brand can produce an assessment of consumer trust in the brand to decide whether to make a repeat purchase or not. The better the brand image a brand has, the greater the potential for consumers to make repeat purchases. The better a brand is assessed, the more positive assessments of the brand will increase which can trigger repurchase intentions.

Opinions or reviews by other consumers that are distributed in a wide scope are still not certain to be able to encourage repurchase intention. Opinions or reviews given by other consumers may not match the preferences of different people. The large number of eWOM received by consumers also causes some consumers to experience difficulties in understanding the content of the information received, resulting in confusion and this influences decision making. Negative electronic word of mouth also influences consumer decisions in making repeat purchases. The higher the frequency of eWOM carried out by other consumers, the more influence it will have on repurchase intention.

Brand image has a significant effect on repurchase intention through customer satisfaction. Brand image is able to influence repurchase intention directly, but customer satisfaction has an important role that can have a greater influence than direct influence. This shows that the influence exerted by brand image on repurchase intention has an indirect effect on the role of the mediating variable, namely customer satisfaction. A good brand image is able to create expectations for consumers who have never made a purchase or used a product so that consumers who are satisfied with the fulfillment of expectations then this influences the consumer's decision to make a repeat purchase. Negative electronic word of mouth cannot create a sense of trust so that consumers have no intention of making repeat purchases. This condition can also occur when there is a difference in the experience received by the consumer himself and the experience of other consumers even though the eWOM received is positive. When this condition occurs, customer satisfaction is not achieved, unable to increase repurchase intention. Likewise, the opinions or reviews provided may not match the preferences of different people so that some consumers have difficulty understanding the content of the information they receive. Negative electronic word of mouth also influences consumer decisions in making repeat purchases.

Limitations in this article that need to be considered for further research are: 1. There have not been many references or previous studies that discuss the insignificant influence of electronic word of mouth on customer satisfaction and repurchase intention, either directly or indirectly. 2. Factors that influence repurchase intention are only limited to being measured using brand image, electronic word of mouth and customer satisfaction variables. Meanwhile, there are many other factors that can influence repurchase intention, such as service quality and brand factors

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